

Modelling Emission Reduction and Climate Change Scenarios in the Dominican Republic: A CLEWS-Based Approach

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- Keywords

Energy system modelling, renewable energy, mitigation, emissions, land use, climate change, OSeMOSYS, CLEWs.

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Executive Summary

This report analyses the impact of climate change effects and mitigation measures in the agricultural and power sectors of the Dominican Republic. The nation's economy is dependent on tourism, agriculture, and manufacturing processes, and is highly vulnerable to climate change impacts because of its insular location and small area.

Through the Climate, Land, Energy, and Water Systems (CLEWs) framework, three scenarios were modelled: Baseline, Nationally Determined Contributions (NDC), and Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). The Baseline scenario presents the current situation of the Dominican Republic regarding agriculture and energy sources and does not include any mitigation measures. The NDC scenario presents a transition of coffee production to agroforestry. Additionally, the IPCC scenario predicts a 15% reduction in precipitation by 2050, impacting water resources and hydropower.

The results show the viability of agroforestry in emissions reduction for the agricultural sector and emphasises the importance of diversifying energy sources to mitigate energy challenges caused by climate change. Policymakers are encouraged to consider innovative solutions and measures for emissions reduction and climate resilience in the Dominican Republic.

1. Introduction

The Dominican Republic is a country located in the Caribbean with a land of 48,442 Km², which depends on tourism, agriculture, and industrial processes as the main sectors contributing to its economy (Ministry of Foreign Affairs, European Union, and Cooperation, 2023, pp. 1-3). According to the Natural Greenhouse Gas Inventory (INGEI) (2015), the primary sectors contributing to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions are energy (61.90%), agriculture (19.90%) and residue (12.90%). Additionally, the country faces several challenges associated with the effects of climate change and it is ranked as 50th on the Global Climate Risk Index 2019 (Ekstein, Künzel, and Schäfer, 2021, p. 45). Given its insular nature and small area, the country is highly vulnerable to maritime influence, hurricanes and rising temperatures, which can cause great harm to their economy (Ministry of Environment and Natural Resources, 2016, p. 9).

Looking to reduce their GHG emissions, the country aims to implement measures to reach a 27% reduction by 2030, aligning with the objectives of their NDC (Ministry of Environment and Natural Resources, 2020, p.5). Given this target, it is crucial to investigate how these planned measures can effectively mitigate emissions, particularly in a sector as important, to the country's development, as agriculture. Additionally, it is essential to analyse how climate change impacts, such as rising temperatures and variations in precipitation, may affect the nation's food security and energy production.

2. Methodology

Three scenarios were created to model the effects on the country using OSeMOSYS, an open-source model generator that works with linear optimisation (Ramos et.al, 2022, p. 698). This model generator can incorporate a Climate, Land, Water and Energy (CLEWs) framework, to analyse the interlinkages of energy and the mentioned sector. This programming model works on the interaction of the systems, identifying the points where the systems interact and establishing data exchange between them. The sectoral models then exchange their data and results, iterating solutions until the most appropriate one is found (Howells, et.al, 2013). The basic energy input data for the model was obtained by using the Starter Data Kit of Paraguay, as the Dominican Republic doesn't currently have a developed dataset. This dataset was then complemented with country-specific values obtained from FAO databases and relevant research papers, for land, energy, and water, as well as energy production data of the Dominican Republic from ClimateScope.

The scenarios were:

- **Baseline:** This scenario explores the country's energy plants, land use, water resources and crop production. There is no cap on emissions or mitigation measurements considered.
- **NDC:** Based on measures regarding NAMA Coffee presented in the country's NDC, the model included a transition in coffee production technology. Over a 15-year period, the production of coffee was shifted from traditional methods to an agroforestry system. This system consists on the combination of crop production with tree integration to provide shade, improve microclimate and capture carbon emissions (CEPAL, 2020, p. 14). This adaptation involved accounting for emissions related to agroforestry systems and implementing production caps on the conventional system to reduce its output.
- **IPCC:** Considering the climate change scenarios established by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) for the Dominican Republic, a 15% reduction in precipitation by the year 2050 was implemented. This had an impact on the water supply for energy generation and agricultural activities within the country.

3. Results

The emissions of CO₂ in the agricultural sector reach a value of 1.04 Mton by year 2070, of this total 0.46 Mton are related to coffee production, as seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Emissions of agricultural crops in the Baseline scenario.

The implementation of an agroforestry system over a 15-year period, starting in 2025 until 2035 is shown in Figure 2. This presents a comparison of the emissions in each scenario. The NDC scenario shows that in 2020, traditional coffee production remained prevalent,

while the agroforestry system began its integration. The NDC scenario shows that by 2035 most of the coffee production was under the agroforestry system, and by 2070 there is no regular coffee production, which leads to negative emissions as a result of the carbon sequestration capability of the agroforestry system.

Figure 2. Comparison in emissions from coffee production between the Baseline scenario and NDC scenario.

Figure 3 includes the total emissions from the agricultural sector, including crops like rice, maize, banana, sugarcane, coffee, and diesel used for agriculture. The baseline projection indicates a consistent rise in emissions over time if no mitigation measures are implemented. In contrast, the NDC scenario highlights the significant potential of the agroforestry system to capture emissions, mitigating the sector's overall impact.

Figure 3. Comparison of total emissions from the agricultural sector between the Baseline scenario and the NDC scenario.

On the other hand, electricity production can also be affected by climate change impacts. It is expected that by 2070 the Dominican Republic will be dependent on hydroelectric power generation, as it will be their main source of power. Figure 4 shows how the demand of hydro power rises through the years, replacing fossil fuels like coal and natural gas, in the baseline scenario.

Figure 4. Energy production by fuel in Dominica Republic for the Baseline scenario

This analysis includes future scenarios generated by IPCC that estimate that by 2050% total annual precipitation in Dominican Republic will have had decreased by 15% due to climate change effects (Ministry of Environment and Natural Resources, 2020, p. 156). This reduction in available water directly affects the water supply which connects to renewable energy production and agricultural production. Figure 5 presents the total hydro energy production in the country for the years 2020, 2050, and 2070 in the baseline scenario and the IPCC scenario, showing a reduction on the capability to meet the demand as in the baseline production.

Figure 5. Comparison of hydropower production between Baseline scenario and IPCC scenario

4. Discussion

Considering the NDC of the Dominican Republic, it is stated that they aim to transform 75,000 hectares of coffee production by 2035 under low-carbon coffee production (Ministry of Environment and Natural Resources, 2020, p.29). This can relate to the establishment of measures like the implementation of agroforestry systems, which have benefits that include increasing plant and animal diversity, regulation of the internal microclimate of the plantation, better conditions for weed control, proper water retention, and reduces soil erosion (IICA, 2016). Apart from this, the trees used to develop this system can capture CO₂ emissions and keep it sequestered for as long as possible, either in the soil or in the form of biomass (Espinoza et. Al, 2012).

The results from this scenario showed that by 2035, most of the coffee production had transitioned to the agroforestry system, with only a small portion of conventional production left. Due to the carbon capture capabilities of the agroforestry system, emissions in the NDC scenario are negative, as it offsets the emissions generated by the conventional coffee production. A similar case is observed in 2070, where conventional coffee production has stopped, resulting in a scenario with no CO₂ emissions and the potential for additional emissions capture. This proves that the agroforestry system is an adequate measure that can be implemented in the country, given its capacity to capture emissions.

The IPCC scenario shows results regarding the decrease in rainfall applied, which may seem modest at 15%, but it has proven to have an impact on energy production. Over time, hydropower assumes a progressively greater role in the country's energy mix. However, by

2050, the limited availability of water begins to influence production, resulting in a reduction compared to the baseline scenario. During the initial years of reduced rainfall, energy production remains unaffected, due to the presence of other alternative power sources. However, as the nation grows and increases its demand for electricity production, the available supply becomes insufficient to meet the needs of the country.

To improve the reach of this study the analysis of livestock production could be included. Enteric fermentation is the main cause for methane emissions, affecting greatly the agricultural sector's overall contribution to emissions. Exploring mitigation measures for this sub-sector can help to achieve a greater reduction of emissions and mitigating the adverse effects of climate change within the country.

5. Conclusion

Developing public policies like NAMA Coffee presents alternative production practices for Dominican Republic's coffee producers. These policies not only offer a structured framework but also provide producers with the necessary guidance and support to implement alternative production methods aimed at reducing emissions. NAMA Coffee present ways to improve innovation and knowledge exchange within the coffee sector looking to adopt environmentally friendly practices that contribute to the country's climate resilience.

Decreased precipitation can affect the water levels in reservoirs and rivers, directly affecting the availability of water for hydropower generation. The results from the IPCC scenario show the need for a better understanding of climate change effects on energy production. While alternative energy sources play a role in mitigating immediate impacts, it is necessary that the country takes action on the long-term challenges posed by changing weather patterns like a diversification on energy sources and implementing energy efficiency measures.

These conclusions emphasize the importance of policy interventions and proactive measures to address climate-related impacts on agriculture and energy production, looking to secure a more resilient future for the Dominican Republic.

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